

of nitrogen to the metal ions^{1,2}. The $\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$ proton signal of the ligand at δ 2.58 shifted to δ 1.86 in the Ti^{III} and Ti^{IV} complexes due to coordination of the carbonyl oxygen of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$ moiety to the metal ions^{1,2}. A multiplet centred at δ 7.0–9.0 due to the phenyl protons of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}=\text{O}$ moiety showing no shift, is observed in the complexes; this rules out the possibility of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen of this moiety.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with some ONO Donor Schiff Bases

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THE synthesis and characterisation of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with the potentially tridentate dibasic Schiff bases (1–4) are described in the present paper.

Substitution

- 1; H
- 2; 5- CH_3
- 3; 3- OCH_3
- 4; 5,6- C_6H_4

Experimental

The ligands 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethylamine hydrochloride, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 5-methylsalicylaldehyde were obtained by Duff's method¹. The Schiff bases were prepared by the reaction of the amine (0.1 mol) and the corresponding aldehyde (0.1 mol) in ether and recrystallised from methanol.

Preparation of complexes: To an ethanol solution of the base hydrochloride (0.1 mol) and the corresponding aldehyde (0.1 mol), aqueous NaOH (0.3 mol) was added with vigorous stirring and the contents were kept on a water-bath until a clear reddish yellow solution was obtained. An ethanol solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was then added to it slowly with constant stirring and the resulting green or pinkish green precipitate was washed with ethanol and ether dried under reduced pressure.

Cobalt and nickel in the complexes were estimated gravimetrically² and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. The molar conductance λ_m (in $10^{-3}M$ DMF), magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values at room temperature, the electronic spectra and ir spectral data were recorded for characterising the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt(II) complexes are pinkish green whereas the nickel(II) complexes are yellowish green. Both the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in solvents like DMF and DMSO. The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) show that the complexes have 1:1 (metal:ligand) stoichiometry indicating the tridentate dibasic behaviour of the Schiff bases. Low molar conductances of the complexes in DMF indicate their non-electrolytic nature³.

The cobalt(II) complexes show two *d-d* bands in 17 000–18 000 and 24 000–26 000 cm^{-1} regions which may be attributed to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(g)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2), respectively. The ν_1 was not observed due to instrumental limitation. However ν_1 was calculated by the method (C)⁴ using the calculated values of $10 Dq$ and B . The values of transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by König's equations⁵. The ligand field parameter B and the ligand field splitting energy ($10 Dq$) in case of the cobalt(II) complexes were calculated⁶. Out of the four methods

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF Co^{2+} AND Ni^{2+} COMPLEXES

Ligand no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Cald.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} cm^{-1}	$\Omega^{-1} \Delta E \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	N			
1	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4)\text{Co}$	15.82 (15.93)	3.74 (3.78)	4.77	17 400, 24 000	9
2	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4)\text{Co}$	15.61 (15.34)	3.55 (3.64)	4.93	17 500, 24 500	11
3	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_5)\text{Co}$	14.17 (14.58)	3.37 (3.46)	4.84	17 000, 25 100	13
4	$(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4)\text{Co}$	14.26 (14.03)	3.10 (3.33)	5.11	17 000, 25 000	22
1	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4)\text{Ni}$	15.61 (15.88)	3.91 (3.78)	3.20	17 240, 26 442	10
2	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_5)\text{Ni}$	14.97 (15.30)	3.53 (3.64)	3.08	17 180, 26 772	12
3	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_5)\text{Ni}$	14.21 (14.54)	3.51 (3.46)	3.24	16 360 27 642	13
4	$(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4)\text{Ni}$	14.02 (13.90)	3.41 (3.30)	3.21	16 130, 27 642	13

applicable in case of the cobalt(II) complexes, the best-fitting method is (C)⁴ because the ratio ν_2 (obs.)/ ν_1 (cald.) is found to be 2.15–2.16 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes and the calculated values of $10 Dq$ is in good agreement to that determined by ν_2 (obs.)– ν_1 (cald.). Thus the electronic spectral data together with μ_{eff} values (4.8–5.2 B.M.) suggest octahedral geometry for all the complexes⁷.

The electronic spectra of the nickel(II) complexes are consistent with their octahedral geometry showing three $d-d$ transition bands at 10 577–11 440, 16 130–17 240 and 26 442–27 642 cm^{-1} , assignable to the transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively⁸. The inter-electronic repulsion parameter B in case of the nickel(II) complexes has been obtained by different methods⁹. Transition energies calculated according to different methods show that the best-fit procedure is the method (C)⁴ as there is small difference in calculated transition energy and observed band energy. Electronic spectral data were used to calculate the important ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, B and λ . For d^8 complexes with OH symmetry, Lever¹⁰ suggested that the configuration interaction between $T_{1g}(P)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ excited states lower the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from 1.8 (theoretical) to 1.4–1.6, which is in conformity with the experimental data supporting the distortion in octahedral geometry. Octahedral geometry is further supported by the μ_{eff} values (2.98–3.24 B.M.) for nickel(II) complexes.

The strong absorption band for the free ligands occurring at 1 620–1 630 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency by 10–15 cm^{-1} in the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes indicating the involvement of

nitrogen atom of azomethine group in coordination¹¹. This is supported by the appearance of a band in the far-ir region 500–535 cm^{-1} due to ν_{M-N} ¹². The absence of a weak broad band due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH to the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group at 2 650–2 700 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicates the deprotonation of both the replaceable hydrogen atoms and the dibasic character of the Schiff bases, leading to the involvement of both the phenolic oxygen atoms in the coordination¹³. This is supported by the appearance of a band at 430–460 cm^{-1} due to ν_{M-O} ¹⁴. The ligands have two phenolic oxygen atoms (one belonging to the salicylaldehyde part of the molecule and the other to naphthylmethylamine part of the molecule). The strong band⁵ near 800–820 cm^{-1} and the broad and weak band⁷ near 3 150–3 200 cm^{-1} of the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes support the formation of a strong M–O bond with the coordinated water molecule.

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Equilibrium Study of the Ternary Complexes of Copper-, Nickel- and Cobalt-(II) with 2,2'-Dipyridyl/*o*-Phenanthroline) and Salicylidene-2-iminopyridine†

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THE present communication deals with the potentiometric study on the complex forming equilibria involved in the ternary complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) or *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) as the primary ligand (A) and the Schiff base salicylidene-2-iminopyridine (SAP) as the secondary ligand (LH) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 30° and ionic strength, $I=0.1\text{ M}$ (KNO_3) adopting Irving-Rossotti method¹ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya².

Experimental

The Schiff base salicylidene-2-iminopyridine was prepared as described earlier³ and dissolved in lime-distilled alcohol to make 0.02 M solution of the ligand. A ECIL 5651 digital pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit), with a combined glass electrode assembly was used for pH-measurement. pH-metric titration technique was followed⁴ for the determination of formation constant values. The following solutions were prepared and titrated against standard alkali solution at 30° in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $I=0.1\text{ M}$ (KNO_3): (a) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (b) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (c) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (d) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (e) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.1 M KNO_3 , and (f) 0.02 M HNO_3 ,

+ 0.1 M KNO_3 . In each case, the total volume was 50 ml. Representative titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated using standard expressions^{1,2}. The results are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Mixed-ligand titration curve of Cu-dipy-SAP system: (a) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M SAP, (b) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP, (c) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP, (d) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy, (e) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy + 0.002 M metal nitrate and (f) 0.02 M HNO_3 ; temp. = 30°; $I=0.1\text{ M}$ KNO_3 (total volume = 50 ml); B = pH meter reading.

Results and Discussion

An observation of the mixed-ligand system (Cu-dipy-SAP) (Fig. 1) reveals that metal-dipyridyl curve (e) diverges from dipyridyl curve (d) at low pH indicating that metal-dipyridyl complex formation takes place at low pH. Calculation of $\bar{n}$ shows that complete formation of 1:1 metal-dipy complex takes place at $\text{pH} \leq 4$. This remains stable upto $\text{pH} \approx 6$, after which metal-dipy curve diverges from the dipy-curve showing formation of hydroxo-species $[\text{M}(\text{dipy})(\text{OH})_n]$. After $\text{pH} \approx 9$, the com-

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